

Deliverable 4.4: BMC SAV Lab Open House

Outreach activities related to cancer prevention

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Basic information

Project title	Strategies to strengthen scientific excellence and innovation capacity for early diagnosis of gastrointestinal cancers
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Nature	R (Document, report);
Dissemination level	PU (Public, fully open, e.g. web);

Executive summary

This deliverable describes activities organized within the VISION project aimed at young people. The main objective of these events was to convey scientific research in an understandable way and motivate and inspire young people/students to study natural science and devote themselves to science. The Slovak Republic has long been struggling with a shortage of young scientists. Therefore, one of the ways to restore research potential is to make scientific work accessible and attractive to young people - from students from secondary schools to undergraduate students. In addition, outreach activities aimed to raise public awareness about the importance of cancer prevention and especially the contribution of lifestyle habits to cancer incidence.

1 Description of work & main achievements

The Covid-19 pandemic and strict restrictions aimed at reducing the gathering of people (2020-2021) did not allow us to open scientific laboratories at the BMC SAV to the students and the general public. Therefore, the regular event - the BMC SAV Lab Open Day - could not take place in those years. However, instead of face-to-face events, various other online activities were held to inform the general public about the VISION project activities, translational cancer research, and the importance of cancer prevention. In 2022, the tradition of making science accessible to students and the general public was renewed after the improvement of the epidemic situation and due to large scale vaccination.

1.1 Science Trade Show

On September 23, 2022, the "Science Trade Show" took place as an open-air event. Besides BMC SAV, many other institutions (universities, private companies, non-governmental organizations, etc.) participated in this event.

Figure 1. Invitation to this event by the organizers.

Figure 2. BMC SAS exhibition stand

Senior scientists and Ph.D. students from BMC SAV have prepared four interactive activities for all those, regardless the age, who are interested in the "mysteries" of science. The main idea was to show that science is exciting and fun. Participants could gain theoretical knowledge (from scientists or instructional videos) and also carry out simple experiments.

Figure 3. Research activities offered by BMC SAV

1.1.1 Make sweet DNA (activity 1)

The aim of activity 1 was to clarify to the participants what deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) is and why it is so important. Illustrative schemes were used to explain to the participants where DNA is located in the cell and its role in living organisms. Each participant could create her/his own sweet DNA using candies (gummy bears and licorice confections) and wooden skewers, representing the basic components of DNA. In a playful way, they could learn the DNA structure and the importance of correct base pairing.

DISCIPLÍNA: VYTVOR SI SLADKÚ DNA

Model DNA z pelendrekov a gumových medvedíkov

Figure 4. The theoretical background to activity 1

1.1.2 Words hidden in genetic code (Activity 2)

Color beads were used to explain to the participants the principle of genetic code - the transfer of genetic information from DNA to protein synthesis. Those who were interested could create a bracelet representing any word encoding by a genetic code..

Figure 5. The theoretical background to activity 2

1.1.3 Colorful science (Activity 3)

Become a magician. The participants could see the changes in color depending on the pH of the solution. By adding citric acid or baking soda to red cabbage juice, different colored solutions were prepared, and the principle of pH-sensitive color reactions was explained. Different color shades of some flowers (forget-me-not, lavender, etc.) are caused by differences in the pH of the soil where they grow.

DISCIPLÍNA: FAREBNÁ VEDA

- **Antokyány - kúzelné farbivá**
- rastlinné pigmenty rozpustné vo vode
- sú zodpovedné za modré alebo fialové sfarbenie rastlín
- zmena farby vplyvom pH
- nízke pH – červené
- neutrálne pH - fialové
- mierne alkalické pH - modré
- veľmi vysoké pH - žlté

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 857381

Figure 5. The theoretical background to activity 3

1.1.4 Isolation of DNA from banana (Activity 4)

DNA is present in all cells of living organisms – from bacteria to humans (except human erythrocytes). The participants could verify this phenomenon – they could isolate DNA from a banana by using a simple procedure.

Figure 6. The theoretical background to activity 4

A short video from this event is available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ivigjw2k5k>

1.2 Course: Advanced Methods in Genetics

On September 6 – 14, 2022, BMC SAV hosted Ph.D. students from Comenius University in Bratislava, Department of Genetics. This course aimed to inform the students about the infrastructure, established methods, and good laboratory practice available at BMC SAV. The students have an opportunity to utilize all types of equipment available at BMC SAV during their Ph.D. study if they are interested. During this course, the senior scientists explained the principles of the individual methods; they made students familiar with how particular devices operate and the data nature of particular equipment types.

Figure 7. Ph.D. students visiting BMC SAV

1.3 Promotion project VISION video

A promotion video was prepared to make the activities planned and organized within the VISION project visible as much as possible. This video is available not only from the VISION website (all domains) but also from the Slovak Academy of Sciences website.

Figure 8. The VISION project was launched in November 2019 in Bratislava

1.4 On Wheels Against Cancer

The On Wheels Against Cancer event tries to draw the general public's attention to the problems of oncology patients, to the urgent need for cancer prevention, and at the same time to involve as many children, youth, adults, and seniors in physical activities as possible. In Bratislava, 2637 people in all age categories participated in this popular event.

Figure 9. Invitation to the event On Wheels Against Cancer

Figure 10. The final control of whether everything is ready for the event.

Before the race

The race stars.....

After the race.....

Snacks for competitors.

1.5 VISION website public domain

A domain for the general public (in Slovak) has been created on the VISION website. Here, those interested can find information about the symptoms, treatment, and prevention of certain oncological diseases and nanomedicine.

VISION
STRATEGIES TO STRENGTHEN SCIENTIFIC EXCELLENCE AND INNOVATION CAPACITY FOR EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF GASTROINTESTINAL CANCERS

ÚVOD
NAŠA MISIA
PARTNERI
NOVINKY
PREVENCIA A LIEČBA
Rakovina hrubého čreva a konečníka
Rakovina pankreasu
Kolonializmus a rakovina
Nanomedicina

Rakovina hrubého čreva a konečníka

V posledných rokoch sa na popredné miesta vo výskyte onkologických ochorení dostal **kolorektálny karcinóm** - najčastejšie nádorové ochorenie tráviaceho traktu. Vo svete je vo výskyte na treťom mieste po karcinóme pľúc a prsníka, na Slovensku je druhým najčastejším zhubným nádorovým ochorením u mužov a tretím najčastejším u žien. Výskyt kolorektálneho karcinómu stúpa s úrovňou industrializácie a je vyšší v ekonomicky vyspelých krajinách, preto ho môžeme zaradiť medzi civilizačné ochorenia.

ÚVOD

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Rakovina pankreasu

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Nanomedicína

Rakovina pankreasu

pankreas = podžalúdková žľaza

Rakovina pankreasu je celosvetovo štvrtou najčastejšou príčinou úmrtia spomedzi všetkých typov nádorov a predpokladá sa, že čoskoro bude **najsmrteľnejším typom rakoviny**. Jedná sa o veľmi agresívne, rýchlo sa rozširujúce ochorenie. Napriek zvyšujúcej sa kvalite zdravotníctva v posledných rokoch počet nových prípadov nádorov pankreasu výrazne narastá a Slovenská republika je na treťom mieste medzi krajinami Európy vo výskyte tohto ochorenia.

TYPY NÁDOROV PANKREASU

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Kolonializmus a rakovina

Nanomedicína

NANOMEDICÍNA

Nanomedicína je relatívne nové, dynamicky sa rozvíjajúce odvetvie medicíny, ktorého cieľom je zlepšiť diagnostiku a liečbu multifaktoriálne podmienených ochorení. Je to interdisciplinárna veda, ktorá spája znalosti biomedicínskych vied (molekulárna biológia, genetika, farmácia, medicína) s poznatkami z nanotechnológie a vedy o materiáloch.

Nanomateriály

Nanomateriál je materiál, ktorého najmenej jeden rozmer má veľkosť v rozpätí 1 až 100 nm. V prípade nanomedicíny sa táto všeobecne akceptovaná definícia rozširuje aj na častice s

2 Deviation from the workplan

The strict restrictions due to the COVID-19 pandemic (2020-2021) did not allow us to welcome students and the general public into the BMC SAV laboratories annually as initially planned in the project. However, immediately after improving the epidemic situation, BMC SAV participated in the event - The Science Trade Show as an alternative to the BMC SAV Lab Open Day. The simple experiments aimed to show children, youth, and adults in an understandable form that science is not only exciting but also fun.

3 Conclusion

Despite unpredictable events (Covid-19 pandemic), most planned activities were realized. In addition, various other outreach activities were realized – BMC SAV hosted Ph.D. students from Comenius University in Bratislava, prepared a promotion video about the VISION project, and informed the general public about the VISION project, its goals, and activities via magazines or mass media. Furthermore, a web domain (in Slovak) was created for the general public to find information about the symptoms, treatment approaches, and prevention of colorectal and pancreatic cancer. Here also, information about perspectives of nanomedicine can be found. Moreover, we supported and helped with the organization of the event On Wheels Against Cancer. Furthermore, BMC SAV closely cooperated with the Slovak Cancer Research Foundation in organizing two very popular events – Young Oncologist Workshop/Award and the Scientific workshop oncology. More information about these activities can be found in deliverables D4.5 and D4.3 (which will be published in May 2023).